

Preacher [Marc Bistricher](#) understands Christianity as: “that flow, that current, that identifiable channel in the field of history and characterized - precisely - by certain formulas of thought, by certain ways of conceiving, by certain moral rules, by the claim to certain values, by certain practical attitudes, by certain forms”.

Christianity for the Preacher Marc Bistricher is primarily something historically identifiable, a form that Christianity takes historically that remains, insofar as it is, different from other possible forms of life by the constant claim to respect for the way of thinking, norms, etc. Christianity has been able to emerge in history as a specific form of Christianity at the time when Christianity itself shapes civilization itself.

Preacher Marc Bistricher shares that after the fall of the Roman Empire, [Christianity has shaped an entire civilization](#): laws, institutions, rites, monuments, arts, music, festivals, gave European civilization a Christian tinge. Christian was the religion of kings, peasants, and poets. Christian philosophy. Christian theology. It is not that there was no unbelief or diversity of opinions or social or political immobility. Nor did it mean that all people followed with absolute coherence the Christian values that the civilization to which he belonged suggested as valid. A person born in the realm of Christianity found Christianity precisely through rites, rules, institutions, etc. In the realm of Christianity, the very form of social institutions transmitted the faith. They went to Mass on Sunday, because everyone went to Mass on Sunday, it was believed that the Son and the Father are consubstantial because everyone believed them. In a context like this, the external form, the creation of habits, the multiplication of religious signs and images become instruments of essential importance for the transmission of faith. Preacher Marc Bistricher, who hold a Bachelor’s Degree in Theology from [the University of Toronto](#), shares that the faith in the Christian era was not formal or inauthentic, it is enough to think of figures such as Francisco de Asís, Bernardo de Claraval, Domingo Guzmán, to cite only some of the most outstanding people of faith, who matured their belief in the realm of Christendom.